

The Effectiveness of Chatbot as an Online Learning Method on Active and Reflective Learning Styles

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Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	
Received: April 05, 2021	<i>The world has been adjusting to an internet-centered life due to the Covid-19 pandemic, pushing experts in the field of information technology to innovate with the creation of applications that can support life during the pandemic. As the world is embracing the uncertainty of the pandemic, the education world has to make adjustments to ensure that teaching and learning process continue through the online learning system. Due to various geographical limitations, students, teachers, and parents in Indonesia find online learning difficult to implement. Considering that this situation results in the decrease in learning outcomes, efforts to improve the effectiveness of online learning by considering significant factors such as learning styles are needed. This study aims to explore the effectiveness of online learning by utilizing chatbot, which is an answering robot application, in learning English. As a learning media, chatbot can assist students who are having problems in learning with its knowledge database. Furthermore, chatbot can also determine the level of practice questions that match the user's ability. It is expected that users can learn independently with chatbot. This study involved 100 students, who were divided into 2 groups, namely the active learning style group and the reflective learning style group. The conclusion is that with the help of chatbots there is an increase in learning outcomes of both active learning style group and reflective learning style group. However, the increase of learning outcomes of the active learning style group is more significant. Through multivariate analysis, the results show that chatbot as a medium for online learning has an effect on the learning outcomes of students with active and reflective learning styles.</i>
Accepted: September 07, 2021	
Keywords : Chatbot, Learning Style, Independent Study, Practice Questions, Active-Reflective	
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5484411	

Introduction

Two individuals who grow up in the same environment and have the same upbringing do not necessarily have the same understanding, thoughts, and views of the world around them. Every individual has their own perspective on every event that they see and experience. This indicates that every individual has different points of view which in turn reflect their learning styles. Experience refers to all of the events that a person has experienced. All events experienced throughout life have an impact to an individual, either positive or negative (Neill, , 2008.).

The success of the learning process in the classroom is reflected by the student's level of understanding towards the materials given in the class by the teacher. Reviewing the materials provided by the teachers can affect the student's level of understanding. Student's understanding can be determined by several factors, including: 1) The way teachers carry out the learning process in the classroom; 2) Learners' learning styles, and 3) The ability of students to retain the lessons delivered by the teacher (Croese, 2011). Teachers should consider the above mentioned factors and consider the solutions by determining the suitable learning process and the learning model to be carried out next.

The teaching and learning processes involve teaching and learning activities which involve the interaction between the teacher, the students being taught, and also the learning resources (Hampden-Thompson & Bennett, 2013)(Hinostrroza, Labbé, Brun , & Matamala, 2011). The end result of this interaction is that it is expected that students who are taught can form their knowledge concepts actively, interactively, and exhilaratively, which in turn can become a solid foundation of the initial knowledge for students to step into higher knowledge (Eckel, Zavaritskaya, & Schüttpelz-Brauns, 2019)(Nursuhud & Darma, 2019).

Before the Covid-19 pandemic, the teaching and learning process relied on the face-to-face method where teachers played a crucial role. The situation changed suddenly when the Covid-19 pandemic occurred. The teaching and learning process, which were previously teacher-centered, have now become student-centered. The pandemic does not allow teachers to implement the face-to-face method as often as in the past. Therefore, online learning is needed to facilitate students in learning. Various problems have risen throughout the implementation

of the online learning method, including: (1) Parents are not ready to become the teachers for their children; (2) There is a lack of interaction between teachers and students; (3) The students' motivation for conducting online learning is still low; (4) The learning style of each student is different, and; (5) There is a difference in the initial knowledge. The impact of these factors cause student's learning outcomes to be unsatisfactory (Pianta & Hamre, 2009) (Rossman & Rallis, 2012).

Learning styles as one of the factors that determine student's learning success can be used as the teacher's reference to improve the learning outcomes when carrying out the teaching process online. Based on the students' conceptual understanding abilities, there are two types of learning styles, namely the field independent learning style and field dependent learning style. The students with these distinct learning styles are shown to have significantly different learning outcomes (Azis & Susanti, 2014). Other research show the same findings. According to the results of studies that support the theory put forward by Reigeluth and Merrill (1979), the learning condition variables are divided into three groups, namely (1) objectives and characteristics of the subject of study, (2) constraints and characteristics of the subject of study, and (3) characteristics of the students (Dedi, 2019).

One of the online learning methods applied in English courses is by using a chatbot application. For example, a Facebook-based social media application uses the organizing exercises items method where the difficulty level of the questions used for training depends on the user's ability level (Sarosa, Kusumawardani, Suyono, & Wijaya, 2020). Similar to other online learning applications, the problem arising from the implementation of the application is that students are unable to achieve the satisfactory scores. According to the research, from the 87 students who learned English using the chatbot application, 69 students obtained grades below the passing standard. Given that the application is feasible to be used as an online learning medium, the effort to improve the students' learning outcomes can be done by implementing chatbot as well as by taking into account of students' learning styles.

Literature Review

Chatbot Learning Media

Chatbot as a conversational agent interacts with users with natural language. Multi chatbots can operate in various domains, but the chatbot's knowledge base is hand coded in its brain (AbuShawar & Atwell, 2015). Chatbot is an intelligent agent with which users can converse both by text or voice. Recently, chatbots have become popular in businesses focusing on client service (Sánchez-Díaz, Ayala-Bastidas, Fonseca-Ortiz, & Garrido, 2018). Chatbots are systems that can interact with humans in a more appropriate way using natural language, and they are becoming increasingly important. This is due to the availability of computational means for natural language interactions between computers and humans which are getting closer to real human interaction (Bozic, Tazl, & Wotawa, 2019). Chatbots can also be used as an automated assistant to help job seekers practice job interview in English. With interviewer machine (interviewer bot), it is expected that students can practice speaking English appropriately for job interview (Sarosa, Junus, Hoesny, Sari, & Fatnuriyah, 2018).

Chatbot is a computer program that can perform automatic tasks, especially on sending messages (Ahmad, Hamid, Zainal, Rauf, & Adna, 2018). Equipped with Artificial Intelligence (AI), chatbots can mimic human conversation (Molnár & Szüts, 2018) (Dale, 2016). Chatbot naturally interacts with users using natural human language and can assist the users in need (Georgescu, 2018.) (Zumstein & Hundertmark, 2017) (Brandtzaeg & Følstad, 2017) In accordance with the development of artificial intelligence, chatbots have been used in various services, for example in automatic telephone answering system, education, business, e-commerce, personal assistant, and entertainment applications, and as task-taking machine which execute tasks ranging from answering questions, providing driving directions, turning on the thermostat at home, or playing favorite songs (Ranoliya, Raghuwanshi, & Singh, 2017) (Pham, Pham, Nguyen, & Nguyen, 2018) (Cui, Huang, Wei, Tan, & Duan, 2017). Currently, chatbot has been drawing researchers' attention as many studies on chatbots have been conducted. Among these, there are commonly researched subjects, such as chatbots functionality in answering Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ), the application of chatbot in education field, or the evaluation of chatbot platforms (Pham, Pham, Nguyen, & Nguyen, 2018) (Saenz, Burgess, Gustitis, & Mena, 2017).

Chatbots can be implemented as a medium for delivering material in education (Sarosa, Kusumawardani, Suyono, & Wijaya, 2020) (Georgescu, 2018.) (Romanelli, Bird, & Ryan, 2009). Conversation using artificial intelligence technique increases the automation in teaching (Sánchez-Díaz, Ayala-Bastidas, Fonseca-Ortiz, & Garrido, 2018). In this case, design knowledge and research are important in developing an engaging and useful media that not only take advantage on the advances in technology, but also understand emotional, cognitive, and social education issues (Bii, 2013). The introduction of chatbots in education in the last decade implies an increasing interest in the application of chatbots for teaching and learning (Alghasham, 2012).

Active and Reflective Learning Styles

Felder (1993) describes an active learner as an individual who needs to do something when learning, while reflective learner is an individual who seek to understand information through introspection and logical processing. Some studies suggest that learning process can be improved when students are classified into different learning style groups. Identifying students from their preferred learning style allows teachers to modify their teaching style to meet with the students learning styles. On the other hand, some others suggest that using teaching style that are not suitable with the students' learning style might actually help students to improve their learning skills. In this case, subjects that can accommodate different learning styles might be the best solution. There are some sets of parameter that reflect the standardization of learning styles. However, as these parameters implement different descriptors of learning styles, they are often scrutinized for not having the capacity to measure learning styles, but rather the learner's personality. As much as the debate goes, eventually, learning styles become an increasingly crucial pedagogical reference, owing to the fact that classes are also becoming bigger in size and more diverse (Romanelli, Bird , & Ryan, 2009).

It is suggested that active learners tend to do better in certain activities where reflective learners do not generally excel in. Conversely, reflective learners excel in other fields that active learners are commonly not strong at. This calls for the teachers to be able to identify their students' learning styles and discuss this with them in order to figure out how much they want their learning process to be tailored to their learning style. In classes where students are not given the opportunity to learn based on their learning style, the students are often time required to make an adjustment by learning some strategies that can compensate the lack of learning that best suit their characteristics of learning (Alghasham, 2012).

The features of e-learning environment create an opportunity for a flexible and dynamic learning experience that can accommodate various learning activities. This way, students with a certain learning style receive lesson with a matching teaching style. It is suggested that students with reflective style learn through the "instruction and recall" teaching style, while those who are characterized as having an active learning style received the "brainstorming" teaching style. There are cases, however, where students are taught through teaching style that do not accommodate their learning styles. In such case, students with reflective style might be taught with brainstorming, while those who are characterized as having an active learning style learn through the instruction and recall teaching style. Reflecting from the instructor's teaching style (brainstorming or instruction and recall) and the students' learning styles (active or reflective) and contemplating from the students' prior domain knowledge, it is suggested that prior knowledge potentially has a significantly positive relation with the pre-test, post-test, and learning styles. Therefore, students' prior knowledge is used as a covariate in this research. This research finds that students whose learning styles match with the corresponding teaching style show significantly greater improvement compared to those whose learning styles are not accommodated by the teachers' teaching style (Hsieh, Jang, Hwang , & Chen, 2011)

Research Methods

The online learning method through Chatbot media is the independent variable in this study, while the learning styles which include active learning styles and reflective learning styles are the dependent variable. The research sample was 100 people with an age range between 16 and 19 years old. The instruments of this study consist of the pretest and post test question instrument and the learning styles adapted from the Felder-Solomon's (2006) Index of Learning Style (ILS).

The diagram of the quasi-experimental pretest and post test nonequivalent control group design (Setyosari, 2010) 2 x 2 factorial design is shown in Figure 1,

O1	X1	Y1	O2
O1	X1	Y2	O2

O1	X2	Y1	O2
O1	X2	Y2	O2

Information:

O1 = Pretest results

O2 = Post test results

X1 = Online learning method through individual chatbot media

X2 = Online learning method through group chatbot media

Y1 = Active Learning Style

Y2 = Reflective Learning Style

Figure 1. The diagram of the quasi-experimental pretest and post test.

The factorial design patterns in the study are as follows:

Table 1. Factorial Design Pattern

		Chatbot Media Learning Strategy	
		Individual (Ind.)	Group (Grp)
Learning Style	Active Learning Style (ALS)	Y111	Y121
		Y112	Y122
	
		Y11n	Y12n
	Reflective Learning Style (RLS)	Y211	Y221
		Y212	Y222
	
		Y21n	Y22n

Information:

Ind = Online learning method through individual chatbot media

Grp = Online learning method through group chatbot media

ALS = Learning Style Aktive

RLS = Learning Style Reflektive

Y = Learning outcomes

Results and Discussion

The hypothesis

This study presents two types of hypothesis, namely the pretest hypothesis and the post test hypothesis. Both hypotheses contain two sections, which are based on chatbot as the online learning media and the learning styles. The following is the description of the hypothesis.

The pretest hypotheses formulated based on chatbot as the online learning media.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pretest based on chatbot as the online learning media,

H_1 : There is a significant difference between the mean scores of the pretest based on chatbot as the online learning media.

The pretest hypotheses formulated based on the learning styles

H_0 : There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pretest based on the learning styles,

H_1 : There is a significant difference between the mean scores of pretest based on the learning styles.

The post test hypotheses formulated based on the online learning media chatbot

H_0 : There is no significant difference between the mean scores of post test based on chatbot as the online learning media,

H_1 : There is a significant difference between the mean scores of post test based on chatbot as the online learning media.

The post test hypotheses formulated based on the learning styles.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between the mean scores of post test based on the learning styles

H_1 : There is no significant difference between the mean scores of post test based on the learning styles.

The Pretest and Post-test Analysis

Learning styles are classified into four: (1) Concrete Experience (CE), which is a learning style based on one's feelings, foregrounding on the experiences and delicately prioritizing on relationships; (2) Abstract Conceptualization, which is a learning style which highlights on student's reception and understanding of materials through logical, systematic, and conceptual thinking; (3) Reflective Observation, which is a learning style of students who learn by observing before assessing, allowing the students to look into a problem from different perspectives which are then being conceptualized into opinion, and; (4) Active Experimentation (AE), which is identified in students who learn through actions, giving the students the faculty of executing tasks and taking calculated risks, as well as the competency of a leader (Kolb, 2015).

In relation to the description above, the results of the pretest and post-test were obtained as follow.

Table 2. The Pretest Mean Scores

Learning Method Categories	Score		Range	Mean	SD
	Min	Max			
Active Learning Style	7,50	23,50	17,00	15,09	4,125
Reflective Learning Style	8,50	25,50	14,50	16,50	3,474

Table 3. The Post-test Mean Scores

Learning Method Categories	Score		Range	Mean	SD
	Min	Max			
Active Learning Style	39,00	47,00	18,00	42,09	3,901
Reflective Learning Style	30,00	44,00	14,00	37,44	3,841

As seen in Table 2, the mean score for the pretest of the sample group classified as Active Learning Style group is lower than the sample group classified as Reflective Learning Style group, wherein the mean score for the Active Learning Style group is 5.09, while the mean score for the Reflective Learning Style group is 16.50. Observed from an increase of score to 42.09 (a rise by 27 points) in the post test mean score for the Active Learning Style group, it can be concluded that the learning outcomes become inversely proportional when online learning with chatbot is implemented. Similarly, the post test mean score for the Reflective Learning Style Group increased by 20.94 points, resulting in post test mean score of 37.44 (Table 3). However, the increase of mean scores between pretest and post-test for the the Reflective Learning Style group is not as significant as that of the Active Learning Style group. It can be concluded that students who have active learning style suit best with online learning method with chatbot.

As seen in the table, the pretest mean score of the Active Learning Style group is lower by 1.41 points than that of Reflective Learning Style group. However, the post test mean score of the Active Learning Style group became higher by 4.65 points than that of Reflective Learning Style group. From this analysis, it can be concluded that the mean scores of the Active Learning Style group and the Reflective Learning Style group based on chatbot as the online learning media have no significant difference. This statement is supported by the data analysis results shown below.

Table 4. The Test Result on Pretest Mean Scores Based on Chatbot as Online Learning Media

	Chatbot as Online Learning Media	
	Equal variances assumed	Equal variances not assumed
Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	F	2.711
	Sig.	.103
t-test for Equality of Mean Scores	T	-.110
	Df	94
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.534
	Mean Difference	-.094655
95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	Std. Error Difference	.77358
	Lower	-1.61317
	Upper	1.45291

Table 5. The Test Result on Pretest Mean Scores Based on Learning Styles

	Learning Styles	
	Equal variances assumed	Equal variances not assumed
Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	F	2.383
	Sig.	.126
t-test for Equality of Mean Scores	t	1.744
	df	94
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.284
	Mean Difference	1.35073
95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	Std. Error Difference	.80561
	Lower	-.18737
	Upper	2.88882

It can be seen in Table 3 that the t-test from the two analyzed learning style groups results in an equality of mean scores with sig. (2-tailed) of $0.534 > 0.05$, which means that H_0 is accepted and H_1 is rejected. This indicates that the mean scores of the pretest based on chatbot as learning media are not significantly different. It can also be seen in Table 4 that the t-test for equality of mean scores with sig. (2-tailed) is $0.284 > 0.05$. It can be concluded that the mean scores of the pretest based on learning styles are not significantly different.

Table 6. The Test Result of Post-test Mean Scores Based on Chatbot as Online Learning Media

	Chatbot as Online Learning Media		
		Equal variances assumed	Equal variances not assumed
Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	F	1.728	
	Sig.	.192	
t-test for Equality of Mean Scores	T	-1.764	-1.758
	Df	94	90.181
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.081	.082
	Mean Difference	-.63851	-.63851
	Std. Error Difference	.36201	.36327
	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	Lower	-1.35730
	Upper	.08027	.08316

Table 7. The Test Result of Post-test Mean Scores Based on Learning Styles

	Learning Styles		
		Equal variances assumed	Equal variances not assumed
Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	F	.271	
	Sig.	.604	
t-test for Equality of Mean Scores	t	.922	.914
	df	94	77.034
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.359	.363
	Mean Difference	.34528	.34528
	Std. Error Difference	.37444	.37756
	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	Lower	-.39818
	Upper	1.08874	1.09710

In Table 5, it can be seen that the t-test for equality of mean scores with sig. (2-tailed) is $0.81 > 0.05$. Similarly, in Table 6, the t-test for equality of mean scores with sig. (2-tailed) is $0.359 > 0.05$. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the post test mean scores based on the online learning method with Chatbot and the learning styles.

Testing of Hypotheses

Data analysis test on the learning outcomes is conducted in order to prove the hypotheses. To do so, multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) test is conducted at 0.05 significance level.

Table 8. The Results from Multivariate Analysis

Multivariate Tests ^a						
	Effect	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.993	6759.079 ^b	2.000	91.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.007	6759.079 ^b	2.000	91.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	148.551	6759.079 ^b	2.000	91.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	148.551	6759.079 ^b	2.000	91.000	.000
Method	Pillai's Trace	.013	.590 ^b	2.000	91.000	.557
	Wilks' Lambda	.987	.590 ^b	2.000	91.000	.557
	Hotelling's Trace	.013	.590 ^b	2.000	91.000	.557
	Roy's Largest Root	.013	.590 ^b	2.000	91.000	.557
Learning Styles	Pillai's Trace	.196	11.062 ^b	2.000	91.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.804	11.062 ^b	2.000	91.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.243	11.062 ^b	2.000	91.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.243	11.062 ^b	2.000	91.000	.000
Learning Methods	Pillai's Trace	.030	1.391 ^b	2.000	91.000	.025
	Wilks' Lambda	.970	1.391 ^b	2.000	91.000	.025
	Hotelling's Trace	.031	1.391 ^b	2.000	91.000	.012
	Roy's Largest Root	.031	1.391 ^b	2.000	91.000	.000
a. Design: Intercept + Method + Learning Styles + Learning Methods						
b. Exact statistics						
c. Computed using alpha = .05						

The analysis of the multivariate test indicates that the test result on the effect of learning methods and learning styles with Pillai's Trace is 0.025, Wilks' Lambda 0.025, Hotelling's Trace 0.012, and Roy's Largest Root 0.000 effect, which all show that significance 0.000 is smaller than 0.05 (sig. < 0.05). It can be concluded that there is an interaction effect between learning methods and learning styles and the attainment of learning outcomes.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the pretest given to the two groups, the difference of mean scores between the two different learning style groups is insignificant. However, after post-test was administered, there is a significant difference in the mean scores of the two learning style groups. Reflecting on this, while Kolb states that each student has a tendency to combine different learning styles to suit the student's need, eventually the said student shows stronger preference to a distinct learning style. The fact that the increase of mean scores between pretest and post-test in active learning style and reflective learning style groups are significantly different serves as a proof that online learning method through the use of chatbot shows a more significant results with the active learning style group rather than with the reflective learning style group.

Table 4 and 5 illustrate the analysis of data taken from pretest, while Table 6 and 7 provide information about the analysis of data taken from the post-test. The t-test for equality of mean scores with sig. (2-tailed) for each condition is > 0.05 (which means that H₀ is accepted). Hence, based on chatbot as the online learning media and the learning styles, the pretest and post-test mean scores do not have significant difference.

The multivariate test gives information about the interaction between the variables of the research. The values of Pillai's Trace, Wilks' Lambda, Hotelling's Trace, and Roy's Largest Root are all less than 0.05. A conclusion can be drawn that both active and reflective learning styles are affected by the implementation of chatbot as online learning media.

Acknowledgment

The researchers would like to express gratitude towards the Directorate General of Research Enhancement and Development, Ministry of Research Technology and Higher Education, for the grant provided through Penelitian Terapan Unggulan Perguruan Tinggi (Higher Education Excellent Applied Research Grant), 2020.

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